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Review Article

**CELLULITIS: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF THE MEDICAL
MANAGEMENT OF CELLULITIS****Vaishnavi Gawande¹, vaishnavi surve², Vinayak katekar³, Swati Deshmukh⁴**^{1,2}Students of Bachelor of Pharmacy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy Kondala Zambre, Washim 444505.³Assistant Professor, Department of Quality Assurance, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy Kondala Zambre, Washim 444505.⁴ Department of Pharmacology, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy Kondala Zambre, Washim 444505.**Abstract:**

Cellulitis is a bacterial infection of the skin, presenting with poorly demarcated erythema, edema, warmth, and tenderness. Although common, it often can be a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge. In this review, the pathophysiology, microbiology, clinical presentation, and risk factors of cellulitis are discussed. Cellulitis can occur in any part of the body especially in legs and face. The bacteria most commonly involved are streptococci and Staphylococcus aureus. When left untreated it affects the lymphatic vessels and reaches the circulation causing serious conditions. The borders of the area of redness are generally not sharp and the skin may be swollen. Lymphatic vessels may occasionally be involved. This review deals about the infection spread, symptoms, investigations, and treatment in cellulitis. The approach to diagnosis is reviewed and the importance of differentiating cellulitis from clinical mimics of cellulitis is highlighted. An approach to empirical treatment is presented, with recent recommendations from the literature. Cellulitis is an infection of the deep dermis and subcutaneous tissue, presenting with expanding erythema, warmth, tenderness, and swelling. Cellulitis is a common global health burden, with more than 650 000 admissions per year in the United States alone.

Keywords: Infection, Management, Cellulitis**Corresponding author:**

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INTRODUCTION:

Cellulitis is a common, potentially serious bacterial skin infection. The affected skin is swollen and inflamed and is typically painful and warm to the touch. An acute spreading bacterial infection affecting the dermis and subcutaneous layer characterized by local findings of tenderness, erythema. Increased warmth, swelling, and regional lymphadenopathy. Cellulitis being a bacterial infection most commonly involves streptococci and staphylococcus aureus affecting the deeper layers of skin. The face and legs which are affected may be swollen and appears red with break in the surface of skin. The local findings are characterized by tenderness, erythema, increased warmth, swelling, and regional adenopathy. (1) Local factors causing cellulitis includes tinea pedis, ulcers. Trauma, and insect bites whereas systemic factors include venous insufficiency (2), lymph edema (3), peripheral vascular disease, diabetes mellitus and obesity.

Cellulitis is usually a superficial infection of the skin (left). But if severe (right) or if left untreated, it can spread into the lymph nodes and bloodstream. Cellulitis usually affects the lower legs, but it can occur on the face, arms and other areas. The infection happens when a break in the skin allows bacteria to enter. Left untreated, the infection can spread to the lymph nodes and bloodstream and rapidly become life-threatening. It isn't usually spread from person to person.

Figure. 1

DEFINITION:

Cellulitis is a deep infection of the skin caused by bacteria. It usually affects the arms and legs. It can also develop around the eyes, mouth, and anus, or on the belly. Normal skin can be affected by cellulitis, but it usually happens after some type of injury causes a skin break, including trauma or surgery. Once the skin breaks, bacteria can enter and cause infection.

KEY POINTS ABOUT CELLULITIS:

- Cellulitis is a deep bacterial infection of the skin.
- Cellulitis usually causes redness, swelling, and tenderness.
- Good hygiene and skin care can help prevent cellulitis.
- Watch any breaks in the skin for signs of infection.
- Untreated cellulitis can lead to amputation, shock, and even death.

SYMPTOMS:

Cellulitis usually occurs on one side of the body. Its signs and symptoms may include:

- An irritated area of skin that tends to expand
- Swelling
- Tenderness
- Pain
- Warmth
- Fever
- Chills
- Spots
- Blisters
- Skin dimpling

CLINICAL CLASSES OF CELLULITIS:

This classification was devised by Eron for skin and soft tissue infections.

Class I: patients have no signs of systemic toxicity, have no uncontrolled co-morbidities and can usually be managed with oral antimicrobials on an outpatient basis.

Class II: patients are either systemically ill or systemically well but with a co-morbidity such as peripheral vascular disease, chronic venous insufficiency or morbid obesity which may complicate or delay resolution of their infection.

Class III: patients may have a significant systemic upset such as acute confusion, tachycardia, tachypnoea, hypotension or may have unstable co-morbidities that may interfere with a response to therapy or have a limb threatening infection due to vascular compromise.

Class IV: patients have sepsis syndrome or severe life-threatening infection such as necrotizing fasciitis

CAUSES:

- Cellulitis is caused when bacteria, most commonly streptococcus and staphylococcus, enter through a crack or break in the skin. The incidence of a more

serious staphylococcus infection called methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) is increasing.

- Cellulitis can occur anywhere on the body, but the most common location is the lower leg. Bacteria are most likely to enter broken, dry, flaky or swollen skin, such as through a recent surgical site, cuts, puncture wounds, ulcers, athlete's foot or dermatitis.

Cellulitis is usually caused when bacteria enter a wound or area where there is no skin. The most common bacteria that cause cellulitis include:

- Group A β – hemolytic streptococcus (Strep)
- Streptococcus pneumoniae (Strep)
- Staphylococcus aureus (Staph)
- Staph and strep bacteria are commonly found on the skin and mucous membranes of the mouth and nose in healthy people. The infection happens when there is a break in the skin that allows the bacteria to enter. Other causes may include human or animal bites, or injuries that happen in water.

RISK FACTORS:

Several factors increase the risk of cellulitis:

- **Injury :**

Any cut, fracture, burn or scrape gives bacteria an entry point.

- **Weakened immune system:**

Conditions that weaken the immune system — such as diabetes, leukemia and HIV/AIDS — increase the risk of infection. Certain medications also can weaken the immune system.

- **Skin conditions:**

Conditions such as atopic dermatitis (eczema), athlete's foot and shingles can cause breaks in the skin, which give bacteria an entry point.

- **Long-term (chronic) swelling of the arms or legs (lymphedema) :**

This condition sometimes happens after surgery.

- **History of cellulitis :**

Having had cellulitis before increases the risk of getting it again.

- **Being overweight:**

Excess weight increases the risk of developing cellulitis.

PREVENTION:

If your cellulitis recurs, your health care provider may recommend preventive antibiotics. To help prevent cellulitis and other infections, take these precautions when you have a skin wound:

- **Wash the wound daily with soap and water** . Do this gently as part of your normal bathing.

- **Ask your health care provider whether it would help to apply a protective cream or ointment.** For most surface wounds, a nonprescription ointment (Vaseline, Polysporin, others) provides adequate protection.
- **Cover the wound with a bandage.** Change bandages at least daily.
- **Watch for signs of infection.** Irritation, pain and pus all signal possible infection and the need for medical care.

People with diabetes or poor circulation need to take extra precautions to prevent skin injury. Good skin care includes the following:

- **Inspecting your feet daily.** Regularly check your feet for signs of injury so that you can catch infections early.
- **Moisturizing your skin regularly.** Lubricating the skin helps prevent cracking and peeling. Don't apply moisturizer to open sores.
- **Trimming your fingernails and toenails carefully.** Take care not to injure the surrounding skin.
- **Protecting your hands and feet.** Wear footwear and gloves suitable to your activities.
- **Promptly treating infections on the skin's surface, such as athlete's foot.** Minor skin infections can easily spread from person to person. Treat fungal infections as soon as they occur.

MICROBIOLOGY:

- **Blood Investigation:**

In blood culture, an elevated level of C reactive protein is a better indicator of bacterial infection than an elevated white cell count but a normal level of C reactive protein cannot rule out an infection. Blood cultures are rarely positive (2-4%) and contaminants may outnumber pathogens. (6) (7) Blood cultures should not be undertaken routinely but be reserved for patients where the infection has been graded as Class III or Class IV where they are more likely to yield the causative organism. Blood investigations do not appear to be clinically useful for diagnosis.

National guidelines, including the Northern Ireland Clinical Resource Efficiency Support Team (CREST) 2005 guidelines on the management of cellulitis in adults, recommend taking blood cultures only inpatients that have significant systemic upset including pyrexia(>38°C).(9)

CREST guidelines suggest the use of skin biopsies and aspirations in only patients, where the diagnosis of cellulitis is in doubt.(9)

Imaging:

Imaging techniques are useful when there is a suspicion of an underlying abscess associated with cellulitis, necrotising fasciitis, or when the diagnosis of cellulitis is uncertain .

Doppler Ultrasound:

It is usually the first investigation to evaluate a clinical suspicion of cellulitis. Normally the subcutaneous tissue is hypoechoic with few hyperechoic strands (representing connective tissue).

In early cellulitis, there is a diffuse increase in the thickening and echogenicity of the subcutaneous tissue; helpful technique is to compare the tissue with contralateral side

Later, there is accumulation of fluid in the subcutaneous tissue, giving it a “cobble-stone appearance” (this appearance is not specific for cellulitis, but is seen in subcutaneous edema due to any cause).

CT:

CT is used to accurately differentiate between superficial cellulitis and deep cellulitis (cellulitis associated with deep-seated infection).

In uncomplicated cellulitis, CT demonstrates skin thickening, septation of the subcutaneous fat, and thickening of the underlying superficial fascia. If the infection spreads to deeper tissues, deep cellulitis, soft-tissue abscess, infectious myositis, necrotizing fasciitis, and osteomyelitis can all be detected with CT. (10)

MRI:

MRI (magnetic resonance imaging) may be useful in those with an equivocal diagnosis of cellulitis or with suspicion of necrotising fasciitis. According to CREST guidelines, in the haemodynamically stable patient an MRI scan is warranted. (9)

Differential Diagnosis:

- Deep vein thrombosis.
- Insect bite.
- Superficial thrombophlebitis.
- Varicose eczema.
- Pyoderma granulosum.
- Chronic venous insufficiency.
- Contact dermatitis.
- Vasculitis.
- Gout.
- Septic arthritis/osteomyelitis.

- Erythema nodosum.
- Drug reaction.
- Severe ischaemia/compartement syndrome.
- Necrotising fasciitis.
- Metastatic carcinoma (carcinoma erysipeloides).

Management of the locally affected area should include the following:

- Adequate analgesia to ensure pain relief
- Monitoring and management of any pyrexia
- Consider hydration – intravenous/oral
- Recording of the site and/or limb affected
- Mark off the extent of erythema present on admission.

DIAGNOSIS:

Diagnosis is usually based on a medical history and physical exam. Blood and skin samples may be taken to confirm the diagnosis and the type of bacteria that is present. A bacterial culture can identify the organism causing the condition and indicate the most effective

antibiotic.

Figure.2

TREATMENT:

Cellulitis treatment usually includes a prescription oral antibiotic. Within three days of starting an antibiotic, let your health care provider know whether the infection is responding to treatment. You'll need to take the antibiotic for the full course, usually 5 to 10 days, even if you start to feel better. Your healthcare provider will consider your age, overall health and severity of the condition when determining the appropriate treatment for you.

General measures include rest, elevation of any affected limbs and analgesia.(12) The area of cellulitis should be clearly marked and reviewed daily for progression or regression to assess the efficacy of the antibiotic regimen.(9)Oral antimicrobials are as

effective as parenteral antimicrobials for the treatment of uncomplicated cellulitis. (4) (6) Topical antibiotics

should not be used in the management of cellulitis in conditions of broken or exuding skin.

Suitable Drug Therapy for Typical Cellulitis:

First line and Second line drugs as per CREST guidelines

	First Line	Second Line
Class I	Flucloxacillin 500mg qds po	Penicillin allergy: Clarithromycin 500mg bd po
Class II	Flucloxacillin 2g qds IV	Penicillin allergy: Clarithromycin 500mg bd IV or Clindamycin 600mg tds IV
Class III	Flucloxacillin 2g qds IV	Penicillin allergy: Clarithromycin 500mg bd IV or Clindamycin 900mg tds IV

Class IV: Benzyl penicillin 2.4g 2-4 hourly IV + Ciprofloxacin 400mg bd IV + Clindamycin 900mg tds IV

(If allergic to penicillin use Ciprofloxacin and Clindamycin only)

Clindamycin is often given as a second-line treatment, if needed. (13)

Flucloxacillin is sometimes given with penicillin V. However, there are no published randomised controlled trials comparing Flucloxacillin monotherapy with a combination of Flucloxacillin and penicillin V in the management of cellulitis. (14)

CREST guidelines still recommend amoxicillin or Flucloxacillin for the majority of cases of cellulitis caused by *S aureus*, *Streptococcus*, or when the organism has not been identified. In those with severe cellulitis requiring admission to hospital, linezolid and vancomycin were found to have good efficacy.(15)

Drug Therapy for atypical cellulitis:

Risk Factor	First Line	Penicillin allergy
Human bite	Co-amoxiclav 625mg tds po	Clarithromycin 500mg bd po Doxycycline 100mg bd po and Metronidazole 400mg tds po
Cat/Dog bite	Co-amoxiclav 625mg tds po	Doxycycline 100mg bd po and Metronidazole 400mg tds po
Exposure to fresh water at site of skin and break	Ciprofloxacin 750mg bd po and Flucloxacillin 500mg qds po	Ciprofloxacin 750mg bd po and Clarithromycin 500mg bd po

Symptoms typically disappear a few days after you start treatment. You may need to be hospitalized and receive antibiotics through your veins (intravenously) if:

- Signs and symptoms don't respond to oral antibiotics
- Signs and symptoms are extensive
- You have a high fever

Getting treated right away can help prevent the spread of cellulitis. Treatment may include:

- Oral, intramuscular (injection), or intravenous (IV) antibiotics
- Cool, wet dressings on the infection site
- Keeping the area dry and clean

- Surgery
- If your arm or leg is affected, elevating the arm or leg may help
- Rest
- Time to heal
- Topical antibiotics
- Pain medicine as needed

Based on the physical exam, your healthcare provider may treat you in the hospital, depending on the severity of the cellulitis. In the hospital, you may get antibiotics and fluids through an intravenous (IV) catheter.

SELF CARE :

Try these steps to help ease any pain and swelling:

- Place a cool, damp cloth on the affected area as often as needed for your comfort.
- Ask your health care provider to suggest a nonprescription pain medication.
- Elevate the affected part of the body.
- Ask your health care provider whether it might help to wear compression wraps or stockings.

COMPLICATIONS :

Complications of cellulitis can be very serious. These can include extensive tissue damage and tissue death (gangrene). The infection can also spread to the blood, bones, lymph system, heart, or nervous system. These infections can lead to amputation, shock, or even death.

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Cellulitis is a clinical diagnosis based on the spreading involvement of skin and subcutaneous tissues with erythema, swelling, and local tenderness, accompanied by fever and malaise. The approach to therapy involves the identification of the likely source as either local (secondary to abrasion or ulcer or due to another exposure, such as an animal bite or seawater, which implicates particular bacterial species *P. multocida* and *V. vulnificus*, respectively) or an uncommon bacteraemia spread of infection. Distinctive features of the patient (such as the presence of diabetes or immunocompromise) or anatomical sites should also be considered in treatment decisions. Streptococci (groups A, G, and B) and *S. aureus* are the most frequently isolated species

CONCLUSION:

Cellulitis is a common and expensive problem worldwide. It generally responds to relatively simple and inexpensive antibiotic regimens; however, recurrent disease is common and can be minimized by optimizing risk factors for cellulitis, such as lymphedema and skin damage. When cellulitis does not respond to treatment, other conditions that mimic it should be considered. Additional research on the diagnosis and management of cellulitis is needed.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

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Disclosure of conflict of interests

The authors have known conflict of interest to declare

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